

Figure S7: Gene ontology of genes in inversions

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|---|---|
| 1. cerebellum vasculature development | 9. lipid localization |
| 2. netrin-activated signaling pathway | 10. neural crest cell differentiation |
| 3. dephosphorylation | 11. phospholipid transport |
| 4. protein processing | 12. cell morphogenesis involved in neuron differentiat... |
| 5. regulation of calcium ion-dependent exocytosis | 13. axon extension involved in axon guidance |
| 6. peptidyl-serine phosphorylation | 14. developmental pigmentation |
| 7. transmission of nerve impulse | 15. regulation of developmental growth |
| 8. calcium-ion regulated exocytosis | |